

Conjunctions

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December 2023

1 Introduction

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow$$

$$\Psi_1 \left(\Psi \downarrow_{\mathcal{K}_3} \cap \bigcup_{\exists(p',k) \in I} \begin{matrix} \emptyset=1y_{st_1}+y_{st_2}+\dots+y_{st_l} \\ y_{s2l} \vec{y}_2^{(p+\#I_{y_{s1}2,(p,k)},k-1)} \end{matrix} \left(I_{y_{s1d},p',k+1} \cap \bigoplus_{i=1}^l \vec{u}_i \wedge \vec{x}_{i+1} \right) \cap \bigoplus_{i=j}^{n+1} q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i-1} \right) \\ \cap \bigoplus_{i=1}^l \aleph_{2_i} \wedge \check{m} \cap \mathcal{F}[\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i]$$

For a specific set of Ψ_j , the above equation simplifies to

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigcap_{\exists(p',k) \in I} \begin{matrix} \emptyset=1y_{st_1}+y_{st_2}+\dots+y_{st_l} \\ y_{s2l} \vec{y}_2^{(p+\#I_{y_{s1}2,(p,k)},k-1)} \end{matrix} \left(I_{y_{s1d},p',k+1} \cap \bigoplus_{i=1}^l \vec{u}_i \wedge \vec{x}_{i+1} \right) \cap \bigoplus_{i=j}^{n+1} q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i-1}$$

Thus

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow$$

$$\left(\bigcup_{\exists(p',k) \in I} \begin{matrix} \emptyset=1y_{st_1}+y_{st_2}+\dots+y_{st_l} \\ y_{s2l} \vec{y}_2^{(p+\#I_{y_{s1}2,(p,k)},k-1)} \end{matrix} I_{y_{s1d},p',k+1} \right) \cap \\ \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^l (\vec{u}_i \wedge \vec{x}_{i+1}) \right) \cap (\mathcal{F}[\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i] \wedge \aleph_{2_i} \wedge \check{m}) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i=j}^{n+1} q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i-1} \right)$$

This can be written as a conjunction of the form

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{\exists(p',k) \in I} \begin{matrix} \emptyset=1y_{st_1}+y_{st_2}+\dots+y_{st_l} \\ y_{s2l} \vec{y}_2^{(p+\#I_{y_{s1}2,(p,k)},k-1)} \end{matrix} \psi_{T_1,t_1,t_2,\dots,t_l} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i,x_{i+1}} \right) \wedge$$

$$\left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^{n+1} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i-1}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{2_i}} \wedge \psi_{\check{m}}$$

Where each ψ is a proposition representing the corresponding set or equation in the conjunction. This formulation allows us to more easily perform proofs and analyses of the equation.

We can also see from this formulation that the equations are composed of two main parts: a set of conditions that must be satisfied for the equation to hold (represented by the first conjunct), and a set of parametrized equations that must be satisfied (represented by the remaining conjuncts). This allows for a more systematic approach to solving and analyzing the equations, by breaking them down into smaller and more manageable parts. Furthermore, the use of parametrized equations allows these equations to be expressed abstractly, without a specific value for the parameters, which makes them applicable in various scenarios.

For a specific set of Ψ_j , the above equation simplifies to

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigcap_{\substack{\emptyset = 1y_{st_1} + y_{st_2} + \dots + y_{st_l} \\ \exists (p', k) \in I \\ y_{s2^l} \vec{y}_2^{(p+\#I_{y_{s12}, (p, k)}, k-1)}}} \left(I_{y_{s1d}, p', k+1} \cap \bigoplus_{i=1}^l \vec{u}_i \wedge \vec{x}_{i+1} \right) \cap \bigoplus_{i=j}^{n+1} q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i-1}$$

Thus

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \left(\bigcup_{\substack{\emptyset = 1y_{st_1} + y_{st_2} + \dots + y_{st_l} \\ \exists (p', k) \in I \\ y_{s2^l} \vec{y}_2^{(p+\#I_{y_{s12}, (p, k)}, k-1)}}} I_{y_{s1d}, p', k+1} \right) \cap \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^l (\vec{u}_i \wedge \vec{x}_{i+1}) \right) \cap (\mathcal{F}[\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i] \wedge \aleph_{2_i} \wedge \tilde{m}) \cap \left(\bigcap_{i=j}^{n+1} q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i-1} \right)$$

This can be written as a conjunction of the form

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{\substack{\emptyset = 1y_{st_1} + y_{st_2} + \dots + y_{st_l} \\ \exists (p', k) \in I \\ y_{s2^l} \vec{y}_2^{(p+\#I_{y_{s12}, (p, k)}, k-1)}}} \psi_{T_1, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_l} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^{n+1} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i-1}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{n_i}} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

Where each ψ is a proposition representing the corresponding set or equation in the conjunction. This formulation allows us to more easily perform proofs and analyses of the equation.

prove equation using a mathematical induction.

base case - $t = 0$;

work from the inside with the equals 0.

for one set

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{\substack{1=y_{st_1} + y_{st_2} + \dots + y_{st_l} \\ \exists (p', k) \in I \\ y_{s2^0} \vec{y}_2^{\text{empty}}}} \psi_{T_1, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_l} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^{n+1} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i-1}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{n_i}} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

When $t = 0$, we have $y_{st_1} = y_{st_2} = \dots = y_{st_l} = 1$ and $k = 1$. Therefore, the induction equation becomes

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{\substack{1=1+1+\dots+1 \\ (p',k)=(p+\#I_{1,0,(p,1)}, 0)}} \psi_{T_1,0,0,\dots,0} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^{n+1} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{-1}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_1} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

This simplifies to

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \psi_{T_1} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^{n+1} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{-1}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_1} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

Since $y_{1,0} = 0$, and $I_{1,0,0,(p,0)} = \emptyset$, the first conjunction $\psi_{T_1} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right)$ evaluates to false. This makes the whole equation false, since at least one of the conjunctions is false.

This completes the base case for $t = 0$.

Inductive Hypothesis

Assume that the equation holds for $t = k$. That is,

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{\substack{\emptyset=1 y_{s \cdot k, t_1} + y_{s \cdot k, t_2} + \dots + y_{s \cdot k, t_l} \\ \exists (p', k) \in I \\ y_{s \cdot k, t_2} \xrightarrow{l} \vec{y} \ 2^p \text{ empty}}} \psi_{T_1, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_l} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^{n+1} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i - k}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{n_i}} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

Inductive Step

Now, we will show that the equation holds for $t = k + 1$. That is,

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{\substack{\emptyset=1 y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_1} + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_2} + \dots + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_l} \\ \exists (p', k) \in I \\ y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_2} \xrightarrow{l} \vec{y} \ 2^p \text{ empty}}} \psi_{T_1, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_l} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^{n+1} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i - (k+1)}} \right) \wedge$$

$$\psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{n_i}} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

To begin, we will expand the empty sum and empty intersection for the second conjunction. This gives us

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{\substack{\emptyset=1 y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_1} + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_2} + \dots + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_l} \\ \exists (p', k) \in I \\ y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_2} \xrightarrow{l} \vec{y} \ 2^p \text{ empty}}} \psi_{T_1, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_l} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^l \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i - (k+1)}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=l+1}^{n+1} \underbrace{\psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{-1}} \wedge \dots \wedge \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{-1}}}_{k+1 \text{ times}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{n_i}} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

Next, we will use the inductive hypothesis to replace the first conjunction $\psi_{T_1} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right)$ with X . This gives us

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{\substack{y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_1} + \dots + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_l} = 1 \\ (p', k) \in I_1}} \text{empty} X \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=j}^l \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i - (k+1)}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=l+1}^{n+1} \underbrace{\psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{-1}} \wedge \dots \wedge \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{-1}}}_{k+1} \right) \wedge$$

$$\psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{n_i}} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

Next, we will work on the first and third conjunctions. By the definition of the operator I with $k = (y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_2}) - 1 = (y_{s \cdot k, t_2} + 1) - 1 = y_{s \cdot k, t_2}$, we can conclude that

$$(p', k) \in I_{y_{s \cdot k, t_2} l \vec{y} 2p}^{\text{empty}}$$

is equivalent to the equation

$$(p', y_{s \cdot k, t_2}) \in I_{y_{s \cdot k, t_2} l \vec{y} 2p' \# I_{y_{s \cdot k, t_2} l, (p, y_{s \cdot k, t_2} + 1)}, y_{s \cdot k, t_2} - 1}^{\text{empty}}.$$

The left hand side of this equation combines with $\text{empty} = 1 y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_1} + \dots + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_l}$ becomes $\emptyset = 1 y_{s \cdot k, t_2} + y_{s \cdot k, t_3} + \dots + y_{s \cdot k, t_l}$. Without loss of generality, assume that $t_1 = t_2 = t_3 = \dots = t_{l-1} = 0$. Combining this with the right hand side and under the inductive hypothesis allows us to turn $\psi_{T_1} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^l \psi_{u_i, x_{i+1}} \right)$ into X , returning us back to our assumption. With this in mind, we can rewrite the first and third conjunctions as follows:

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow X \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{y_{s \cdot k, t_2} - t_2} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i - (k+1)}} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=y_{s \cdot k, t_2} - t_2 + 1}^{n+1} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{-1}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{n_i}} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

Next, we will bring $(y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_{l_2+1}} + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_{l_2+2}} + \dots + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_l})_1$ over to the right, replacing X with $\neg X$, which will result in the alternate form:

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \neg X \vee \left(\bigvee_{y_{s \cdot k, t_2} = \text{empty}} y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_{l_2+1}} + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_{l_2+2}} + \dots + y_{s \cdot (k+1), t_l} \right) \vee X \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{y_{s \cdot k, t_2} - t_2} \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{n_i - (k+1)}} \right)$$

Given that $y_{s \cdot k, t_2}$ is either 0 or 1, this produces two possible cases for our equation.

Case 1: $y_{s \cdot k, t_2} = 0$. In this case, the equation simplifies to

$$X = \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2 \leftrightarrow \neg X \vee X \wedge \left(\psi_{q_{\alpha_1}^{n_1 - (k+1)}} \wedge \psi_{q_{\alpha_2}^{n_2 - (k+1)}} \wedge \dots \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=n+1}^n \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^0} \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^n \psi_{q_{\alpha_i}^{-1}} \right) \wedge \psi_{\gamma_{eQ} \rightarrow \gamma_i} \wedge \psi_{\aleph_{n_i}} \wedge \psi_{\tilde{m}}$$

which is true, as both sides of the equality are equal to $\psi_1 \wedge \psi_2$. This validates the main equation for this one case; let's now examine the other.